

The Influence of Ocular Allergy on Quality of Life

Kumar Magar^{1*}, Sankhajyoti Saha²

¹Ganga Eye Care Centre, Kumarikata, Assam-781360, India

²NSHM Knowledge Campus-Kolkata Group of Institutions, Kolkata-700053, India

Corresponding author.

E-mail address: kumarmagaroptom@gmail.com (K. magar)

Received 28 August 2025, Accepted 10 September 2025, Available online 26 September 2025.

ABSTRACT

Ocular allergy is a spectrum of bilateral inflammatory response, with a prevalence of 12–20%, and its occurrence has increased significantly over the past four decades. By constraining daily activities, it typically affects 15–20 % of the global population, substantially reducing health-related quality of life (QOL), consequently inhibiting social involvement and efficiency. The current research initiatives to assess the impact of ocular allergy on the QOL, exploring the clinical impacts. This observational, cross-sectional study inspects the impact of ocular allergy on QOL in a cohort of individuals aged 18 to 60 years, with established inclusion and exclusion criteria. This study employed a modified type of the RAND 36-Item Health Survey (SF-36) to assess the quality of life of patients with ocular allergy with targeted modifications, followed by a pilot study, which showed acceptable ranges of reliability and internal consistency. Visual functioning was found to be strongly associated with social functioning ($r=0.771$) and pain ($r=0.726$); however, ocular and emotional role limitations were significantly correlated ($r=0.911$). The statistical association between energy/fatigue and general health ($r=0.551$) and emotional well-being ($r=0.604$) was modest. Visual functionality, social involvement, and pain perception constitute the components of quality of life that are most significantly impacted by ocular allergies. Older individuals were involved with higher functional and role limitations, emphasising the heightened susceptibility of this population. Such conclusions illustrate the urge for a holistic approach to addressing ocular allergies that is extensive and involves lifestyle modifications, psychological interventions, and symptomatic improvement.

Keywords: Ocular allergy, allergic conjunctivitis, quality of life, health survey, visual functioning

Introduction

Ocular allergy, frequently signified by the term Allergic Conjunctivitis (AC), is a spectrum of bilateral inflammatory response affecting the conjunctiva and/or cornea to the environmental allergens, differentiated by intense ocular itching, which is its identifying feature, with clinical presentation contrasting according to the characteristics and intensity. Concurrently, itching, burning sensations, photophobia, irritation, and discomfort substantially influence visual efficacy and quality of life [1, 2]. Acute allergic conjunctivitis is generally categorised into two types: seasonal allergic conjunctivitis (SAC) and perennial allergic conjunctivitis (PAC). Additionally, three chronic inflammatory conditions affect the

conjunctiva and cornea: vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC), atopic keratoconjunctivitis (AKC), and giant papillary conjunctivitis (GPC) [3]. From a clinical perspective, the more prevalent and less intense variants include SAC, which is frequently stimulated by pollen-heavy seasons, and PAC, which persists throughout the year against the allergens, including dust mites, animal dander, or feathers. Symptoms manifest as watering, redness, chemosis, and microscopic papillae (<0.3 mm) contained within the eyelids. Severe versions occur with the inclusion of the cornea and encompass Vernal Keratoconjunctivitis (VKC), predominantly affecting young men, and worsening in the spring and summer and Atopic Keratoconjunctivitis (AKC), which is often associated with chronic eczema in adults. Collectively, these clinical subtypes,

spanning from insignificant conjunctival irritation to corneal involvement that constitutes an imminent visual risk, exhibit the distinct manifestation of ocular allergies [1, 2]. AC is a prevalent ocular condition, with a prevalence rate of 12–20%, and its occurrence has increased significantly over the past four decades due to urbanisation, industrialisation, pollution, and dry-eye syndrome. Males are relatively more susceptible than females, with dust reported as a primary contributing factor, and concurrent medical conditions consisting of allergic rhinitis, dermatitis, and asthma have been reported. Considering its burden, the tendency to seek treatment is insignificant; around 57% refrain from pursuing consultation, and around 4.6% respond to recommended treatment. The condition, which is consistently recurrent and rarely severe, frequently remains underdiagnosed, considerably contributing to the public health burden of ocular allergies [3-11]. The pathogenesis of ocular allergy incorporates an aberrant relationship among Th1 and Th2 cells and their cytokine identities, resulting in enhanced immune responses. Emerging literature suggests that several cytokines, chemokines, proteases, and growth factors interact across intricate, interrelated transactions instead of intuitive intersections. The stimulation of non-specific enzymatic pathways during acute and chronic inflammation contributes to tissue damage and preserves hypersensitivity, emphasising the multifaceted and adaptive mechanisms that contribute to the onset and evolution of ocular allergic ailment [12]. By constraining daily activities, ocular allergies typically affect 15–20 % of the global population, substantially reducing health-oriented QOL (HRQOL). The manifestations, including itching, redness, and watering, render it troublesome to read, use a digital device, and go outside, which eventually inhibits social involvement and efficiency. A significant strain on regular activities and general well-being, as well as persistent discomfort and psychological suffering, emerges from the seasonal symptoms that certain individuals encounter, as well as those that others sustain throughout the year [13]. The ongoing study

initiatives aim to assess the impact of ocular allergy on the quality of life (QOL) of affected individuals. It precisely aims to identify specific aspects of QOL that are most affected by ocular allergy. Additionally, the objectives involve exploring the clinical presentations of ocular allergy and their respective impacts on QOL.

Material and Methods

This is an observational, cross-sectional study conducted at Jupiter Eye Care, Bankura, from June 2025 to August 2025, aimed to inspect the impact of Ocular Allergy on QOL in a cohort of individuals aged 18 to 60 years. Comprehensive inclusion and exclusion criteria had been established to ensure the uniformity of the study population. Our study included participants of both sexes with the occurrence of symptoms characteristic of ocular conjunctivitis, with itchy eyes, that can be associated with discomfort consisting burning sensations, dryness, redness, sensations of a foreign body, tearing, conjunctival congestion, plasma or mucus discharge, and/or bulbar conjunctival/eyelid edema, and presence of SAC, PAC, VKC, and AKC, diagnosed by an ophthalmologist or an optometrist. Individuals with the potential to acknowledge and preparedness for the questionnaire are also included in the study. Consequently, the study will not comprise participants with the presence of other significant ocular diseases (e.g., glaucoma, cataract) that could independently affect QOL. Severe systemic illness that might impact the ability to complete the questionnaires, alongside infectious and/or drug-toxic conjunctivitis, autoimmune keratoconjunctivitis, dry eye, or specific lacrimal duct ailments, was prohibited to confirm diagnostic specificity and exclude other differential etiologies. The analysis will exclude non-respondents and those who will submit questionnaires with either duplicate or insufficient data. Employing the standard formula for sample size estimation, $n = [Z^2 \times p \times (1 - p)] / d^2$, the calculation was performed with a prevalence (p) of 30% [14], confidence level of 95% ($Z = 1.96$), and margin of error of 5% ($d = 0.05$). Considering

these values, $n = 322.6944$; rounding up, the minimum sample size was determined to be 323 participants (**Table 1**). Thus, the estimated sample size required is approximately 323. This study employed a modified version of the RAND 36-Item Health Survey (SF-36) to evaluate the QOL of patients with ocular allergy. While the SF-36 provides a robust measure of general health, it lacks specific items addressing the unique symptoms and impacts of ocular allergy. To enhance the instrument's sensitivity and relevance to this population, targeted modifications were implemented. Patients often report difficulty with everyday visual tasks involving objects, such as locating, directing, guiding, and checking objects. While walking, symptoms may interfere with the ability to fixate or avert gaze effectively, leading to decreased confidence in orientation. In social interactions, ocular allergy can also affect visual engagement; individuals may readily turn towards and fixate on a picture or person, but often find it difficult to maintain eye contact, sometimes deliberately avoiding looking at the same person due to persistent symptoms [15,16]. Collectively, these modifications focused on incorporating items that directly reflect the ocular symptoms and functional limitations experienced by patients with ocular allergy. The Institutional Ethics Committee of the NSHM Knowledge Campus-Kolkata Group of Institutions, Kolkata, assigned ethical approval to obtain the study protocol (Ref. No: NSHMKOL/IEC/5/2025/PR-04), ensuring that the declaration's standards have been adhered to. All participants provided their informed consent before participation. The RAND 36-Item Health Survey will be scored according to standard procedures. A pilot study was executed to determine the amended questionnaire's preliminary validity. Cronbach's alpha was employed to determine internal consistency and item correlations, and exhibited acceptable levels of reliability between sub-scales. Following these methods, the tool's compatibility for utilisation with the initial study population was validated. Two-sided $p < 0.05$ will be the threshold for statistical significance. 95 %

confidence intervals will be incorporated for all significant conclusions, and SPSS will be employed for all analyses.

Results

Considering a mean age of 27.4 years (range 16–51), the descriptive statistics indicate a reasonably younger demographic. Visual functioning ranged considerably within the quality-of-life categories (mean 290.6 ± 278.5 , range 0–1000), demonstrating distinct ranges of visual functioning. Ocular (mean 265.6 ± 1669.9) and emotional (mean 216.2 ± 113.4) role restrictions were both reported as moderately impaired, illustrating that vision-related impairments influenced both emotional and daily functioning. Substantial psychological burden was identified by the group's energy/fatigue (mean 175.1 ± 53.5) and emotional well-being (mean 136.2 ± 81.1) perceptions. Although general health (mean 178.2 ± 60.9) reflected concerns regarding overall health perception, social functioning (mean 96.0 ± 43.7) and pain (mean 102.5 ± 43.5) scores expressed substantial limitations. The clinical significance of these outcomes demonstrates that visual difficulties can lead to considerable functional, emotional, and social constraints in relatively young individuals, emphasising the need for an extensive assessment that transcends beyond visual acuity.

In accordance with the correlation study, age was adversely connected with pain, social functioning, role constraints (both emotional and ocular), and visual functioning (all $p < 0.001$). This implies that growing older is associated with deteriorating functional outcomes and greater discomfort. It's remarkable to observe that age and general health had a positive association ($r = 0.286$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that older individuals exhibited a more improved perception of their general health irrespective of their visual function restrictions. Visual functioning was found to be strongly associated with social functioning ($r = 0.771$) and pain ($r = 0.726$); however, ocular and emotional role limitations were significantly correlated ($r = 0.911$). These outcomes obtained considerable inter-domain

associations. The statistical association between energy/fatigue and general health ($r = 0.551$) and emotional well-being ($r = 0.604$) was modest (**Table 2**). From a clinical perspective, these outcomes recommend that age is a significant modulator of functional degradation and that ocular symptoms profoundly influence the social, emotional, and pain-related components of quality of life.

Reliability

The reliability assessment of the modified questionnaire exhibited a Cronbach's alpha of 0.747 for each of the domains, which was enhanced to 0.866 when standardised items were taken into consideration. The scale's components are effectively correlated in assessing the fundamental premise of quality of life in a clinically relevant approach, as seen by the strong internal coherence and reliability (**Table 3**).

Regression Analysis

Age has been reported to serve as an independent and significant predictor for the most of the domains, comprising Visual Functioning ($\beta = -0.22$, $p < 0.001$), Role Limitation (Ocular) ($\beta = -0.255$, $p < 0.001$), Role Limitation (Emotional) ($\beta = -0.26$, $p < 0.001$), Social Functioning ($\beta = -0.27$, $p < 0.001$), Pain ($\beta = -0.286$, $p < 0.001$), and General Health ($\beta = 0.287$, $p < 0.001$). This implies that, with the notable exception of general health, in which the impact was positive, ageing was correlated with impaired functioning and more constraints in a broad array of quality-of-life domains. Conversely, in each domain (all $p > .20$), the variable Gender was not significant in predicting outcomes. With the potential exception of Energy/Fatigue ($R^2 = 0.002$, $p = 0.683$) and Emotional Well-Being ($R^2 = 0.008$, $p = 0.258$), nearly all the domains had substantial general model fits, with the explained variance (R^2) being acceptable, spanning from 2% (Energy/Fatigue) to 8.3% (Pain and General Health). Consequently, age appears to be a significant predictor of quality-of-life responses, although gender had no impact on the outcomes studied (**Table 4**).

Discussion

The investigation evaluated the multidimensional interactions for assessing the multifaceted impact produced by ocular allergies on quality of life. Based on the outcomes, the effect of ocular allergies not only enhances visual functioning but also broader physical, emotional, and social components of health. Age had a positive relationship with the assessment of overall health, but was considerably inversely related to visual functioning, role limitations (ocular and emotional), social functioning, and pain. Concerning this, elderly individuals may have increased functional impairment from ocular allergies, while they can also have an improved opinion of their general health, which could be an instance of age-specific adaptation or a decreased perception of their health. Visual functioning instantaneously impedes social interactions and enhances discomfort, as seen by the significant positive associations identified across visual functioning, social functioning, and pain. Identical patterns have been observed in research on allergic conjunctivitis and ocular surface disorders, where it has emerged that visual impairment profoundly inhibits participation in social and professional endeavours. The significant connection between emotional role limitation and ocular role limitation emphasises the interaction between psychological stress and physical ocular symptoms. In contrast to prior research indicating that chronic ocular allergies are linked with discomfort, irritation, and an aberration in emotional well-being, individuals who are incapable of accomplishing routine activities related to their allergy are also susceptible to experiencing emotional distress.

The precise interrelationships were identified among social functioning and pain, with almost desirable correlations. This outcome indicates that ocular discomfort, itching, and pain are not separate manifestations but broaden to impede interpersonal affiliations and routine activities. Comparably, moderate-to-strong correlations involving energy/fatigue and emotional well-being with other domains insinuate that ocular allergy has a systemic trigger, impacting

psychological health, and life contentment. These outcomes reverberate considering prior quality-of-life observations in ocular

allergy, where individuals stipulated irritability and reduced work productivity, in addition to ocular dissatisfaction.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Quality of Life Domains

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	340	16	51	27.38	10.423
Visual Functioning	340	0	1000	290.59	278.454
Role Limitation (Ocular)	340	0	400	265.59	166.938
Role Limitation (Emotional)	340	0	300	216.18	113.421
Energy/Fatigue	340	0	400	175.12	53.533
Emotional well-being	340	0	500	136.18	81.117
Social Functioning	340	0	200	96.03	43.650
Pain	340	0	200	102.54	43.453
General Health	340	0	475	178.24	60.910
Valid N (listwise)	340				

Table 2: Correlations of Quality of Life Domains

Correlations										
		Age	Visual Functioning	Role Limitation (Ocular)	Role Limitation (Emotional)	Energy/Fatigue	Emotional well-being	Social Functioning	Pain	General Health
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.222**	-0.253**	-0.258**	-0.035	0.055	-0.272**	0.287*	0.286**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.515	0.314	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Visual Functioning	Pearson Correlation	-0.222**	1	0.525**	0.354**	0.372**	0.609**	0.771**	0.726**	0.53
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.329
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Role Limitation (Ocular)	Pearson Correlation	-0.253**	0.525**	1	0.911**	0.318**	0.208**	0.658**	0.737**	-0.207**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Role Limitation (Emotional)	Pearson Correlation	-0.258**	0.354**	0.911**	1	0.297**	0.068	0.545**	0.663**	-0.216**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001		<0.001	0.213	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Energy/Fatigue	Pearson Correlation	-0.035	0.372**	0.318**	0.297**	1	0.604**	0.596**	0.610**	0.551**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.515	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Emotional well-being	Pearson Correlation	0.055	0.609**	0.208**	0.068	0.604**	1	0.601**	0.528**	0.546**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<0.001	<0.001	0.213	<0.001		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.314	<0.001	<0.001	0.213	<0.001		<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Social Functioning	Pearson Correlation	-.272**	.771**	.658**	.545**	.596**	.601**	1	.943**	.082
	Sig.(2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001		<0.001	0.132
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
Pain	Pearson Correlation	0.287**	0.726**	0.737**	0.663**	0.610**	0.528**	0.943**	1	0.36
	Sig.(2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001		0.511
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340
General Health	Pearson Correlation	0.286**	0.053	-0.207**	-0.216**	0.551**	0.546**	0.082	0.36	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	<0.001	0.329	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.132	0.511	
	N	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	340

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3: Reliability Statistics of Quality of Life Domains

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardised Items	N of Items
0.747	0.866	8

Table 4: Regression analysis of Quality of Life Domains

Domain	R Square	ANOVA Sig.	Age (Beta)	Age (p-value)	Gender (Beta)	Gender (p-value)
Visual Functioning	0.05	<0.001	-0.22	<0.001	-0.032	0.546
Role Limitation (Ocular)	0.066	<0.001	-0.255	<0.001	0.026	0.626
Role Limitation (Emotional)	0.068	<0.001	-0.26	<0.001	0.032	0.548
Energy/Fatigue	0.002	0.683	-0.033	0.549	-0.035	0.526
Emotional Well-being	0.008	0.258	0.057	0.292	-0.069	0.206
Social Functioning	0.075	<0.001	-0.27	<0.001	-0.046	0.382
Pain	0.083	<0.001	-0.286	<0.001	-0.037	0.482
General Health	0.083	<0.001	0.287	<0.001	-0.008	0.882

Conclusions

This research describes that ocular allergy exhibits a substantial and multidimensional influence on quality of life, stepping ahead of visual discomfort to determine emotional well-being, social participation, role functioning, and general health. Visual functionality, social involvement, and pain perception constitute the components of quality of life that are most significantly

impacted by ocular allergies. An effective correlation between domains comprising visual functioning, social functioning, and pain reflects the interdependent tendency of physical and psycho-social repercussions of ocular allergy. Older individuals were involved with higher functional and role limitations, emphasising the heightened susceptibility of this population. Such conclusions illustrate the urge for a holistic approach to addressing ocular allergies that is extensive and involves lifestyle

modifications, psychological interventions, and symptomatic improvement. Prospective researchers should incorporate preventive and longitudinal methods to better comprehend the association of pharmacological, behavioural, and environmental factors that could minimise the significant consequences of ocular allergies on quality of life. Progressively, comprehensive insights may also be obtained by incorporating subgroup analyses (by age and gender, for instance) and ailment grading.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding Acknowledgment

No funding was received for this study.

Declaration of Generative AI in Scientific Writing

The authors affirm that no generative AI or AI-assisted techniques were utilised in the development of this publication.

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